

Effects of Cashless Policy on Business Activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government Area, Kano State

Umar Abdulkadir Zango¹

abdulkadir4rl@gmail.com

+2348029805463

Salmanulfarisi Abdulrahman²

Salmanulfarisiabdu338@gmail.com

+2348062353295

Mallam Abdullahi¹

abdullma75@gmail.com

+2348039433291

Isah Adam Auwal³

auwalisaadam@gmail.com

+2348032777312

¹Department of Business Education, Faculty of Vocational and Technical Education, Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education, Kano State.

²Department of Business Administration, Yusuf Maitama Sule University, Kano, Kano - Nigeria

¹Department of Business Education, Faculty of Vocational and Technical Education, Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education, Kano State.

³Department of Business Education, School of Vocational and Technical Education, Aminu Kano College of Islamic & Legal Studies, Kano

Abstract

This study investigates the Effects of cashless policy on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government Area, Kano State. Three research objectives, corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, respectively guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of seven hundred and twenty-three (723) shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local government, Kano State. Sample size of 248 Shoe Sellers were selected using research advisor's table. Instrument used to collect data for this study is cashless policy and business activities (CAPABA) Questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts, the reliability correlation coefficient of 0.728 was obtained using Cronbach alpha method. Regression analysis was used to analyse the data at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that internet banking, point of Sales and Automated Teller Machine had significant effect on business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Kano State. Base on the findings it was concluded that cashless policy affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon gari market. It was further recommended that association of shoe Sellers in the market should collaborate with internet service providers to improve internet connectivity within the market, workshops and seminars to educate sellers on cashless transactions and digital financial services to be conducted at regular intervals.

Keywords: *cashless policy, business activities, shoe sellers and Market*

Introduction

The emergence of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has led to great revolutionary developments in finance, economics, and operations, which included the development of electronic payment instruments as well. Electronic payment instruments have come to the attention and attracted the attention of researchers for the importance of their vital role in the current era of electronic commerce (Ekpiwre & Haruna, 2019). As a result, it leads to different perspectives on the definitions of cashless, among others, from different perspectives, ranging from finance, business technology, to information systems. Ajayi (2014) defines cashless as a form of financial instrument, where buyers and sellers are facilitated by electronic

Effects of Cashless Policy ... (Zango, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432555>

communication. More specifically, cashless payments as electronic value payments, transacted from payer to recipient through a comprehensive electronic payment channel, which allows payers to freely access and manage their transactions through electronic networks.

Cashless policy is an economy where transaction can be done without necessarily carrying physical cash as a means of exchange of transaction but rather with the use of credit or debit card payment for goods and services. The cashless economy policy initiative of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) is a move to improve the financial terrain but in the long run sustainability of the policy will be a function of endorsement and compliance by end-users. The CBN cash policy stipulates a daily cumulative limit of N150, 000 and N1, 000,000 on free cash withdrawals and lodgments by individual and corporate customers respectively in the Kano, State with effect from March 30, 2012. Individuals and corporate organizations that make cash transactions above the limits will be charged a service fee for amounts above the cumulative limits (Daniel 2020).

The introduction of electronic banking, online transactions and mobile banking in Nigeria has paved way for a new era of development where the use and demand for physical cash is gradually declining. These recent evolution of technology in the Nigerian financial institutions possess interesting questions for economist, financial institutions, business analyst and the government regarding the current economic status, logistics, and availability of instruments to guarantee economic growth and stability, efficiency and effectiveness of the cashless policy (Humphrey, 2021). The CBN and Pro cashless policy activists have asserted reduction in crime rates, minimized risk associated with carrying huge sums of money, reduction in political corruption, reduction in banking cost, improvement on monetary policy in management of inflation and the overall growth and development of the economy of Nigeria as advantages associated with the implementation of the cashless policy (Humphrey, 2017). The recent evolution of technology for financial transactions poses interesting questions for policy makers and financial institutions regarding the suitability of current institutional arrangements and availability of instruments to guarantee financial stability, efficiency and effectiveness of monetary policy. Over the course of history, different forms of payment systems have been in existence. Initially, 'trade by barter' was common; however, the problems of barter such as the double coincidence of wants necessitated the introduction of various forms of money. Nevertheless, analysts have been predicting the complete demise of study instruments and the emergence of potentially superior substitute for cash or monetary exchanges, that is, 'cashless society'.

According to Sabi (2014) the advent of internet technology has revolutionised the way business and services are provided by companies and businesses all over the world. It provided innumerable service innovations for the consumer. They started using the internet technology to deliver banking and financial services. The technological change has brought the rapid transmission of information, the easy way for marketing banking products and enhanced the customer's access and awareness. Banks can use the opportunities offered by the internet as strategic tools and revolutionised the way they operate.

Point of Sale (POS) terminals are deployed to merchant locations where users swipe their electronic cards through them in order to make payment for purchases or services instead of using raw cash. As the POS terminals are online real-time, the customers bank account is debited immediately for value of purchases made or services enjoyed. The POS terminal is also known as a POP terminal and is used for instant payment of goods and services, as it is user-friendly, easy to operate, and has multi-functional capabilities (Mohammed, Ibrahim & Muritala, 2022). POS terminals allow customers to access their linked bank accounts in real-time through debit or credit cards (Iwedi, 2017). They are considered by Awoniyi (2022) as a virtual replacement for cash transactions.

Osang (2017) view POS terminal as a device deployed in a merchant location that allows users to swipe their electronic cards to make payments instead of using physical cash (Williams et al 2018). The adoption of POS terminals has significantly reduced the volume of cash-based transactions, as such adoption of POS technology allows cardholders to make payments at sales or purchase outlets without the need for physical cash. Automated Teller Machines will be used much frequently for making variety of online payments such as utility bills, T.V subscriptions, GSM recharges, customers are advised to keep their ATM cards (Debit and Credit) safe and never to divulge their PINs in sabon gari market in fagge local government area of kano state.

Statement of the Problem

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has implemented a cashless policy to encourage electronic transactions and reduce reliance on cash. While the policy aims to improve financial inclusion and economic growth, its effects on small businesses like shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government Area, Kano State, remains unclear.

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This study investigates the effects of the cashless policy on the business activities of shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market. Specifically, the research will explore the challenges faced by shoe sellers in adopting the cashless policy, such as lack of access to technology, customer resistance to cashless payments, and limited financial literacy.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to determine the effects of cashless policy on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government Area, Kano State. Specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the extent degree at which internet banking transactions affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.
2. To examine the effects of points of sales (POS) transactions on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.
3. To examine the effects of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transactions on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Research Questions

This Study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. To what extent does internet banking transactions business activities among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?
2. To what extent does points of sales (POS) transactions affects business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?
3. To what extent does ATM transactions affects business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Internet banking transactions has no significant effects on business activities among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.
2. Points of sales (POS) has no significant impact on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.
3. Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transactions has no significant impact on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of seven hundred and twenty-three (723) shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local government, Kano State. Sample size of 248 Shoe Sellers were selected using research advisor's table. Instrument used to collect data for this study is cashless policy and business activities (CAPABA) Questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts, the reliability correlation coefficient of 0.728 was obtained using Cronbach alpha method. Regression analysis was used to analyse the data at 0.05 level of significance. The questionnaire was divided into sections according to the two specific purposes and research questions. Responses to items in the questionnaire were based on a four-point Likert-type rating scale, ranging from strongly agree (SA) (4 points), to agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points), and strongly disagree (SD) (1 point).

The questionnaire was administered by the researchers to the shoe Sellers with an explanation on how to fill it. The researchers used descriptive and correlation statistics in analysis of the data. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Mean rating below 2.5 was rejected while any rating of 2.5 and above was accepted.

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Results

Research question one: To what extent does internet banking transactions affects business activities among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?

Table 1 Mean rating of responses on the impact of internet banking transactions on business activities among shoe sellers.

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
1	Convenient and efficient way to manage finances.	3.21	0.54	Agreed
2	Allows you to pay bills online.	3.21	0.54	Agreed
3	Allows you to make online purchases.	3.23	0.58	Agreed
4	Allows you to manage your bank accounts online.	3.24	0.56	Agreed
5	Allows you to apply for loans online.	3.22	0.58	Agreed
Cumulative mean		3.22	0.56	Agreed

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Decision Rule = 2.50

The analysis of item 1-5 used to answer research question one was presented in table 1 indicated that, the mean score of all the five items were found to be greater than the index score of 2.50 for agree, this can also be seen in the cumulative mean value found to be greater than the index score for agree (3.22>2.50) with the standard deviation of 0.56. The analysis therefore indicated that internet banking transactions affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Research question two: To what extent does Points of Sales (POS) transactions affects business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State?

Table 2 Mean rating of responses on the impact of POS transactions on business activities among shoe sellers.

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
6	Allows me to process payments.	3.23	0.55	Agreed
7	Used to track inventory levels	3.18	0.56	Agreed
8	Used to manage my customers data	3.21	0.53	Agreed
9	Used to generate my purchases reports	3.19	0.57	Agreed
10	Used to generate my sales reports	3.25	0.56	Agreed
Cumulative mean		3.21	0.55	Agreed

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Decision Rule = 2.50

The analysis of item 6-10 used to answer research question two was presented in table 2 indicated that, the mean score of all the five items were found to be greater than the index score of 2.50 for agree, this can also be seen in the cumulative mean value found to be greater than the index score for agree (3.21>2.50) with the standard deviation of 0.55. The analysis therefore indicated that POS transactions affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Research question three: To what extent does ATM transactions affects business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Table 3 Mean rating of responses on the impact of ATM transactions on business activities among shoe sellers.

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
11	Impacted my business transactions	3.27	0.56	Agreed
12	Easier for you to conduct business	3.29	0.57	Agreed
13	Saved time and money	3.32	0.54	Agreed
14	Made you more likely to do shoe business.	3.32	0.54	Agreed
15	Safer and secured	3.32	0.54	Agreed
Cumulative mean		3.30	0.55	Agreed

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Decision Rule = 2.50

The analysis of item 11-15 used to answer research question three was presented in table 3 indicated that, the mean score of all the five items were found to be greater than the index score of 2.50 for agree, this can also be seen in the cumulative mean value found to be greater than the index score for agree (3.30>2.50) with the standard deviation of 0.55. The analysis

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therefore indicated that ATM transactions affects business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fegge local government area, Kano State.

Hypotheses

The null hypotheses were tested as follows:

Hypothesis One: Internet banking transactions has no significant effects on business activities among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Table 4 Summary of regression analysis on effect of Internet banking transactions on business transactions among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market.

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sig
1 (Constant)	1.829	0.174	10.535	0.484	.234	0.231	0.000
Internet banking	0.461	0.053	8.675				

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Table 4 revealed a computed significant value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05). This implies that independent variable (internet banking) contributed significantly to variation of business activities. Independent variable (internet banking) explains the variation of dependent variable (business activities) by 0.234% (R²=0.234). It's also indicated that our estimation using this model could only be wrong by 0.053% (Standard error of estimate = 0.053). The table also reveals that for every one unit increase in use of internet banking, there would be an increase in business activities by 0.461 (B=0.461). This implies that internet banking has significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result can be represented in regression equation as business activities = 1.829 + 0.461 (internet banking).

Hypothesis Two: Points of sales (POS) has no significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State.

Table 5 Summary of regression analysis on effect of Points of sales (POS) transactions on business transactions among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market.

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sig
1 (Constant)	1.654	0.171	9.673	0.532	.283	0.280	0.000
Points of sales	0.516	0.052	9.843				

Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Table 5 revealed a computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05). This implies that independent variable (Points of sales) contributed significantly to variation of business activities. Independent variable (Points of sales) explains the variation of dependent variable (business activities) by 28.3% (R²=0.283). It's also indicated that our estimation using this model could only be wrong by 5.2% (Standard error of estimate = 0.052). The table also reveals that for every one unit increase in use of point of sales, there would be an increase in business activities by 0.516 (B=0.516). This implies that point of sales had significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result can be represented in regression equation as business activities = 1.654 + 0.516 (point of sales).

Hypothesis Three: Automated Teller Machine (ATM) has no significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge local government area, Kano State

Table 6 Summary of regression analysis on effect of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transactions on business transactions among Shoe sellers in Sabon Gari Market.

Summary Model	B	Standard Error	T	Rical	R ²	Adjusted R	Sig
1 (Constant)	1.000	0.151	6.615	0.703	.494	0.492	0.000
Automated Teller Machine	0.700	0.045	15.500				

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Source: Result of data Analysis (2023).

Table 6 revealed a computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05). This implies that independent variable (automated teller machine) contributed significantly to variation of business activities. Independent variable (automated teller machine) explains the variation of dependent variable (business activities) by 49.4% ($R^2=0.494$). It's also indicated that our estimation using this model could only be wrong by 4.5% (Standard error of estimate = 0.045). The table also reveals that for every one unit increase in use of automated teller machine, there would be an increase in business activities by 0.700 ($B=0.700$). This implies that automated teller machine had significant effect on business activities among shoe sellers, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result can be represented in regression equation as business activities = 1.000 + 0.700 (automated teller machine).

Discussion

The finding in Table 4 related to null hypothesis one revealed that, internet banking had a variance at 23.4% ($R^2=0.234 \times 100$). This means that for every one unit increase in use of internet banking, there would be an increase in business activities. The computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05) indicating a significant impact. This implies that internet banking had a significant impact on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government, Kano State. This findings is in line with study of Dedi SS, Agil FI, Putri A. (2019) showed that internet banking can have a real influence on e-commerce development if properly administered.

The finding in Table 5 related to null hypothesis two revealed that, point of sales (POS) had a variance at 28.3% ($R^2=0.283 \times 100$). This means that for every one unit increase in use of POS, there would be an increase in business activities. The computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05) indicating a significant impact. This implies that POS had a significant impact on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government, Kano State. This findings is in line with study of Mbah S, Obiezekwem J. (2019) opined that there is positive relationship between POS transactions and performance of SMEs.

The finding in Table 6 related to null hypothesis three revealed that, Automated Teller Machine (ATM) had a variance at 28.3% ($R^2=0.283 \times 100$). This means that for every one unit increase in use of ATM, there would be an increase in business activities. The computed sig value of 0.000 which is less than level of significance (0.05) indicating a significant impact. This implies that ATM had a significant impact on business activities among Shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, Fagge Local Government, Kano State. This findings is in line with study of Saudah W. & Kosala C. K. (2017) opined that ATM transactions had a significant effect to the customer's satisfaction.

Conclusion

This study concluded that Internet banking, points of sales (POS) and Automated Teller Machine (ATM) had significant effects on business activities among shoe Sellers in Sabon Gari Market, fagge Local Government Area, Kano State.

Recommendations

- The following recommendations were given from the findings of the study:
1. The Shoe Sellers Association should encourage sellers to utilize online marketplaces to reach a wider customer base and accept online payments.
 2. The Association of shoe Sellers in the market should collaborate with internet service providers to improve internet connectivity within the market.
 3. The Sabon Gari Market Authority should be conducting workshops and seminars to educate sellers on cashless transactions and digital financial services.
 4. There should be a collaboration with market traders, banks and financial institutions to develop tailor-made financial products and services.
 5. The shoe sellers should promote the use of mobile wallets such as MTN MoMo and Airtel Money for convenient and secured transactions.

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